

DTO-BioFlow

Integration of biodiversity monitoring
data into the Digital Twin Ocean

D2.8 Report on the impact of missing data

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D2.8 – Report on the impact of missing data

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Glossary of terms

Item	Description
AofA	Area of Application
DG-MARE	Directorate-General Maritime Affairs and Fisheries
DTO	Digital Twin of the Ocean
DUC	Demonstrator Use Case
EC	European Commission
EDITO	European Digital Twin of the Ocean
EMODnet	European Marine Observation and Data Network
EurOBIS	European node of OBIS
FAIR	Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability of digital assets
FAO	Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations
FRA	Fishery Restricted Area
GFCM	General Fisheries Commission for the Mediterranean
GSA	Geographical Sub-Area
ICES	International Council for the Exploration of the Sea
MPA	Marine Protected Area
MSFD	Marine Strategy Framework Directive
SDM	Species Distribution Modelling
VME	Vulnerable Marine Ecosystem
WFS	Web Feature Service
WoRMS	World Register of Marine Species
WP	Work Package

Keywords

Biodiversity data, missing data, EU DTO, missing data matrix, risk-based approach

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

D2.8 “Report on the impact of missing data” analyses the potential impact of missing data on the ability to develop digital solutions in a functional DTO environment. Biodiversity and associated pressures data and/or products currently included in EMODnet, and hence into the EDITO infrastructure serving the EU DTO, were assessed through an adaptable multi-stage methodology. First a missing data matrix was developed to assess the missing data in the available platforms such as EMODnet; second a risk-based approach was combined with this first assessment to evaluate the impact of missing data in the DTO. In order to deal with different data features in terms of coverage and resolution, a series of classification factors were designed. After defining criteria and core elements for identifying missing data and for guiding the assessment, semi-quantitative assessments were developed setting the scene on European sea regions (including Mediterranean and Black Seas). The outcomes of this first step, expressed as percentages of missing data, were then grouped and entered as input for an objective-based risk assessment to provide critical insights on applicability of digital solutions. The methodology presented here was designed to be a tool as flexible as possible to provide useful information for data mobilization efforts (T2.4, T2.5). An *ad-hoc* selection process allowed adaptation of the methodology to specific requirements of a digital solution and/or user’s targets. The last part of this deliverable summarizes the relevant outcomes of some applications of the developed methodology with the overarching goal of providing a picture of the current impact of missing data on hypothetical digital solutions within the DTO infrastructure. The main outcomes from the assessment of missing data status indicated that 7 regions are poorly covered in terms of occurrence data, particularly before 1970 and in the last time range analysed (i.e., 2020_2025). Furthermore, high percentages of missing data were found for metagenomics records currently included in EMODnet. In respect to the risk-based assessment, overall, the applicability of generalized digital solutions resulted in low/medium level of risk; however, the application of more complex modelling approaches (e.g., ecosystem models, ecological niche modelling, machine learning) may require mitigation measures, since the resulting overall risk was high, especially when a digital solution requires all the biodiversity data currently at hand. This underlines the importance of a large and sustained flow of data on biodiversity towards EMODnet enabling a functioning DTO that can effectively support the EU to deliver on its biodiversity goals.

Table of Contents

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	5
1. Introduction	7
2. Objectives	8
3. Methodology	8
3.1. Criteria: Area of applications	8
3.2. Elements for the assessment of missing data impact.....	9
3.2.1. Classification factors	10
3.2.2. Information extraction.....	13
3.2.3. Scoring & selection process	13
3.2.4. Missing data Matrix	16
3.3. Impact assessment	16
3.3.1. Impacts definition (severity)	17
3.3.2. Likelihood definition	17
3.3.3. Risk rating key.....	18
4. Examples of applications	18
4.1. Occurrence by phyla in EMODnet.....	18
4.1.1. Occurrence by macro-groups	20
4.2. Metagenomics data by phyla & drivers in EMODnet.....	20
4.3. Risk-based assessment by area of application.....	21
5. Conclusions	24
6. References	25
7. Appendix.....	27
7.1. EMODnet layers	27
7.2. DTO’s georeferenced marine regions: an investigation on suitable biogeographic domains	32
7.2.1. References	34
7.3. Risk Assessment.....	34

1. Introduction

More than 36,000 known species of marine plants and animals are found in Europe (Costello & Wilson, 2011), and understanding their geographic distribution, abundance and seasonal, annual or decadal variation is key to detecting changes in the marine ecosystem and for assessing ecosystem health of maritime basins. Relevant data are often collected with limited spatial and temporal scope and are scattered over different organisations in small datasets for a specific species group or habitat. In addition, as data are collected by multiple organisations, using different standards, technologies and conventions, it is challenging to combine them.

To overcome these challenges and account for the huge and scattered marine data landscape, over the years the European Union has encouraged and supported the creation of a network capable of including most of the available marine data within a single platform. The European Marine Observation and Data Network-EMODnet-was thus created in 2009 as the marine data service of the EC Directorate-General Maritime Affairs and Fisheries (ECDGMARE) EMODnet data covers disciplines organized in 7 thematic lots: bathymetry, biology, chemistry, geology, human activities, physics and seabed habitats. A list including all the available layers within EMODnet platform is provided in 7.1. EMODnet layers. Application of the platform is provided in a user-base across various sectors, including the EU Digital Twin of the Ocean (DTO).

The DTO requires sustained flows of data on biodiversity and associated pressures to digitally replicate the ocean’s ecology. One of DTO-BioFlow's objectives is to establish such sustained data flows. Following this objective, semi-automated data flows have been set up from various sources to EMODnet by sharing the data in standardized data packages compliant with the international standard for biodiversity data: Darwin Core, allowing to treat the data fields in a standardized way (Wieczorek et al., 2012).

Another objective of DTO-BioFlow is the implementation of eight “demonstrator” policy-relevant use cases (DUCs), tasked in WP4 of DTO-BioFlow (T4.1, T4.2; Figure 1) to demonstrate the design and development of a digital replica of real biodiversity systems; hence, an identification of gaps in data flow and analytical services or in their integration into products was required and therefore carried out through the analysis of existing data, sleeping data and operating monitoring networks by WP2.

Figure 1 – Concise workflow between WP2 (Increasing the flow of relevant biodiversity data) and WP4 (Demonstrate with policy-relevant use cases the benefit of an end-to-end approach for biodiversity monitoring) showed with triangles. Circles referred to specific task (T) within the WP: T4.2 is about the Identification and coverage of gaps to integrate and assimilate new data sources into existing models and analytical resources, while T4.1 as for Development and implementation of the Demonstrator use cases (DUC) to deliver an end-to-end approach for biodiversity monitoring through the digital environment.

The ability of digital solutions (biodiversity/ecosystem models and applications) to represent reality and forecast future scenarios is potentially hampered by missing data. **Missing data** is defined as data that are lacking or absent because the data does not exist or is unavailable or inaccessible. In this deliverable, we evaluate the impact caused by missing data, envisaging different scenarios, while keeping the focus on the Demonstrator Use Cases (DUCs) design in Work Package (WP) 4. To do this, an adaptable multi-stage methodology was developed: i) a missing data matrix was adopted to assess the missing data in available platforms such as the European Marine Observation and Data Network (EMODnet); ii) a risk-based approach was combined with this first assessment to evaluate the impact of missing data. The missing data matrix is a tool providing a semi-quantitative assessment on availability of biodiversity data and serves as a basis for a risk-based approach aimed at understanding the consequences of missing data on the applicability and suitability of potential digital solutions envisaged in the DTO-BioFlow project.

2. Objectives

To facilitate the increased flow of relevant biodiversity monitoring data into the DTO, a task within WP2 is to analyse the biodiversity data landscape by identifying missing and hence necessary data to enable a functioning DTO to support the EU to deliver on its biodiversity goals.

The main goal of Task 2.3 is to examine the consequences of missing data on the potential of digital solutions (i.e., biodiversity/ecosystem models and their applications) to represent reality and predict future scenarios. The deliverable is mainly aimed to give a feasible and comprehensive picture of the status of missing data on biodiversity and associated pressures currently included in EMODnet. Through the development of general workflows, this deliverable also assesses the applicability of modelling approaches with different complexity levels with a risk-based approach.

3. Methodology

3.1. Criteria: Area of applications

Criteria for identifying missing data and guiding the assessment of their impact considered the following three areas of applications (Figure 2): (i) sustainable management of sea resources (e.g., Marine Protected Area (MPA), Fishery Restricted Area (FRA), Vulnerable Marine Ecosystem (VME)); (ii) monitoring marine ecosystem health (e.g., fish/shellfish abundance & distribution; protected, endangered and threatened species abundance, biomonitoring and distribution); (iii) resilience of coastal communities to climate change and anthropogenic stressors (e.g., habitat disturbance, invasive species, marine traffic & marine litter). These areas of application aim at providing critical insights on the potential impact of missing data on the ability of different digital solutions to represent reality and forecast future scenarios in different domains.

Figure 2 – Conceptual areas of applications of missing data impact assessment. For each of the three areas an example of possible applications is also shown in brackets.

3.2. Elements for the assessment of missing data impact

The workflow outlining the multi-stage methodology developed to assess the impact of missing data is shown in Figure 3. Each element of the assessment will be explained in detail in the following sections.

Figure 3 – Detailed flow chart of schematising the assessment procedures of the missing data impact. Panel A shows the process to obtain and categorize missing data; while panel B includes the multi-stage assessment of missing data impact: 1. Scoring, 2. Selection process, 3. missing data assessment through missing data matrix, 4. Impact assessment with a risk-based approach.

In compliance with already adopted features in the DTO digital infrastructure, biodiversity and pressures data should be firstly characterised by type, i.e., **response variable** (e.g., biomass and/or occurrence) and **drivers** which consist in

all the variables affecting, also partially, the biodiversity information (e.g., environmental or human pressure data). Therefore, the missing data assessment's method consists of three **core elements**: response variables, drivers and classification factors, flowing into a process aimed at categorizing the missing data. Two **catalogues**, one for the response variables and another for the drivers (Figure 3, panel A, information extraction), were developed in the form of hierarchical databases by including a fixed number of rows (Connolly & Begg, 2002). The number of rows in the databases represent all the combinations among the levels of the classification factors (Figure 4, classification factors). For each row, a **score** (for details see section 3.2.3) was assigned based on ranking the data availability (Figure 1 Figure 3, panel B.1, scoring). After this scoring stage, a **selection process** was conducted resulting in different outcomes by filtering specific levels of the classification factors (Figure 3, panel B.2, selection process). This step was developed to be able to investigate the missing data scores across different data coverages and resolutions, thus making the outcomes more concise and user-friendly (e.g., section 4.1). The resulting missing data assessment was summarized with percentages in the form of a **missing data matrix**, where data coverage and resolution are the dimensions, while the matrix format is the framework for the combination of these data features (Figure 3, panel B.3, missing data matrix). Finally, the missing data assessment flows into a **risk assessment** aimed at examining the suitability and applicability of digital solutions (i.e., modelling approaches; Figure 3, panel B.4, risk assessment). The risk was evaluated through a rating key (for details see section 3.3) based on two criteria: likelihood accounting for the percentage of missing data, and the impact representing the capability to attain the product (e.g., the DUC). The result is a risk level from low to high for each modelling approach assessed, outlining consequences of missing data on the potential of digital solutions to represent reality in a flexible and semi-quantitative way.

3.2.1. Classification factors

Five **classification factors** were designed to summarize all the information in terms of coverage and resolution, in order to satisfy all the possible dimensions and features of the data currently at hand as well as of those not (yet) available or accessible (i.e., sleeping data). These classification factors have been defined based on the current characteristics and dimensions of the data contained in the EMODnet Biology lot: taxonomical resolution, spatial coverage, temporal coverage, spatial resolution, and temporal resolution. Figure 4 shows the different levels for each factor together with their hierarchical position.

Figure 4 – Classification factor chart.

3.2.1.1. Taxonomic domain

In order to develop a methodology able to adapt to different needs and/or availability of information, it was decided to define the species level as the highest **'taxonomic resolution'**; by this way it will be possible to evaluate the impact of missing data for different taxonomic aggregations, whether they are due to the product's needs (i.e., input data) or to the lack of information for specific observations (e.g., impossibility to identify organisms to species level). The taxonomic resolution is therefore defined with the following levels of the classical Linnean taxonomic system: species, genus, family, order/class. In the specific case we are evaluating the impact of the missing data for which the taxonomical resolution is meaningless, as for instance a bathymetry layer, such a classification factor will not affect the scoring process ([section 3.2.3](#)).

3.2.1.2. Spatial domain

After an investigation on suitable biogeographic domains (appendix [section 7.2](#)), a standard for georeferenced marine regions within the DTO-BioFlow's pipeline was selected in WP2. The selected spatial domain had to be in accordance with the default geographical standards of EMODnet Biology, and with the biogeographical aspects for the collection, organization, analysis and modelling of biodiversity data and pressures. Therefore, the 17 ICES ecoregions (ICES, 2023) were adopted to define the **'spatial coverage'** classification factor, since they are currently available as layers within the EMODnet platform and allow to identify sub-areas in agreement with the MSFD (i.e., EU Marine Strategy Framework Directive), and with FAO geographical sub-areas (GSAs), divisions, and subdivisions ([Figure 5](#)).

Figure 5 – ICES ecoregions overlapped with FAO fishing statistical sub-areas, divisions and sub-divisions (upper map) with a focus on FAO-GFCM (General Fisheries Commission for the Mediterranean) geographical sub-areas (GSAs) within the Mediterranean and Black Seas (lower map).

Commonly, data flowing into the EMODnet includes geographical coordinates with a standard map projection. This information was then used to define the ‘**spatial resolution**’ as classification factor, taking into account the possible need to convert the data from one cartographic projection to another for EMODnet product visualization purposes. The possibility that the EMODnet products are used directly as layers instead of raw data – as evidenced in some DUCs - has also been considered. Furthermore, associated biodiversity data, as abundance indices from fishery-dependent surveys, are often provided in aggregated form of and/or catches per unit effort (CPUE). For these reasons a lower level of the spatial resolution factor describing spatial data in aggregate form (e.g., local, regional, by country or by sea) was defined.

3.2.1.3. Temporal domain

Seven different levels were designed as time ranges of the ‘**temporal coverage**’ factor:

- 1880:1909 (historical)
- 1910:1939 (historical)
- 1940:1969 (historical)
- 1970:1999 (historical)
- 2000:2009 (present)
- 2010:2019 (present)

- 2020:2025 (present)

Data collected before 2000 were treated as the historical ones embedded in four levels of 30 years each, while data from 2000 to 2025 (chosen as last year, since it is the delivery year of this report) embodying the present time with three levels of 10 years each. The last time range is to be considered adaptable depending on the actual year in which the assessment is carried out; given that new accessible datasets are flowing -as time passes- into EMODnet through for example the data grants organized in T2.5. The ranges were designed to be adaptable enough also for future applications of the methodology presented here. In the same context of flexibility, 1880 was assumed as the starting year ensuring to include hypothetical historical datasets submissions (e.g., [EMODnet NEWS ARTICLE, 19 December 2024](#)). This is important considering the relevance of historical data to set baselines for marine ecosystem (McClenachan et al., 2012), considering different modelling approaches (Ribeiro et al., 2018; Vitelletti et al., 2023). For ‘**temporal resolution**’, 3 different levels were designed according to EMODnet standards. The minimum temporal resolution was annual/multi-annual. Considering that a monitoring survey could take place several times during the year, an intermediate level of temporal resolution (i.e., season/month) was also defined. Finally, the maximum level of temporal resolution was set as daily/weekly, to facilitate an evaluation of high-resolution data like mooring and telemetry data.

3.2.2. Information extraction

Within EMODnet Biology platform, open access to aggregated data is made available as .csv files where both the biological information as well as associated parameters are included. The list of all fields included in EMODnet Biology is provided through the website (<https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/en/biology>). Data were downloaded from EMODnet directly into an R environment by means of the EMODnet_Web Feature Service (WFS). EMODnet_WFS package allows users to select data sources (called services and arranged into thematic lots) and layers intended as the units of data that machine clients can query, retrieve, and manipulate through WFS. It was then possible to get all the data currently available based on some predefined criteria for both response variables and drivers. The choice among the nature of response variables (e.g., occurrence, abundance index, etc..) or drivers (e.g., seabed habitat, marine litter, etc..) to be used in the assessment is strictly linked to the input data requested by the digital solution. For practical and synthesis reasons, this deliverable will only present assessments on some of the available EMODnet layers ([section 4.2](#)), however the methodology is flexible enough to be applied to other response variable/drivers as needed.

The information was then arranged into a **hierarchical database**. To match with the spatial domain (i.e., ICES Ecoregion) an extraction of the geometry of the occurrence point was carried out, while for the temporal coverage each record was assigned to the corresponding time range. Records outside the spatio-temporal domain were excluded from the analysis. Since each database row represent a specific combination among all the levels of classification factors, the records matching the same row do not add valuable information in this assessment framework; in that case they were scored as a single record avoiding replicates.

3.2.3. Scoring & selection process

To perform the assessment of missing data both for response variables and drivers, the two hierarchical databases were designed with the same number of rows, thus considering all the possible combinations among all the levels of the classification factors previously defined. The mathematical rationale behind such a scoring process is here outlined.

By defining f as the classification factor, the number of all the possible combinations among all the levels of the classification factors is defined as n_{row} , and formulated as follows:

$$n_{row} = \prod_{f \in F} \dim(f) \tag{1}$$

Where F is the set of classification factors and $dim(f)$ is the number of levels for each factor f . For example, if we have five different factors with a different number of levels for each one as: spatial coverage (17 levels), spatial resolution (two levels), temporal coverage (seven levels), temporal resolution (three levels), and taxonomical resolution (four levels); the resulted $nrow$ will be 2856.

To perform a semi-quantitative missing data assessment, different scores based on the data availability were applied:

$$score_f = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if the data are fully available} \\ 0 < x < 1, & \text{if the data are partly available} \\ 1, & \text{if the data are missing} \\ NULL, & \text{if the data do not exist \textbackslash outside the domain} \end{cases}$$

Where NULL indicates that the $score_f$ is not applicable (i.e., meaningless database row for the response variable/driver considered), as direct result of the selection process (see below). Therefore, the formula for assessing the missing data for each single cells of the missing data matrix will be:

$$MD_{s,l} = \frac{\sum_{f \in F} score_f}{n_{row} - score_f(NULL)} \quad (2)$$

where s is the taxonomical resolution, l the layer intended as response variable type (e.g., occurrence, abundance, etc...) or driver's layer (e.g., bathymetry, seabed habitat, vessel density, etc...), and f the classification factor.

In the **scoring process**, each database row was evaluated by means of an assessment key (Figure 6). The key includes discrete and continuous numbers to score resolutions and coverages respectively, where: 0 indicates the absolute availability of information and 1 the total absence of information, while all intermediate numbers represent partially available/missing data.

Figure 6 - Assessment key.

The hierarchy of databases allows us to assign scores by propagating them for lower resolution levels. For instance, if for a certain spatio-temporal coverage (e.g., Baltic Sea, 2020-2025) the information (e.g., occurrence of *Sabellidae*, a family of *Polychaeta* class) is present at an annual resolution with geographical coordinates, then a score 0 will be assigned also for the combination with lower spatial resolution level (e.g., local, regional, by country or by sea). Such a discrete scoring propagation is also applied for temporal and taxonomical resolutions; following the previous example, the record is identified at family level, therefore it will score as available data (i.e., 0) even for taxonomic levels with lower resolution (i.e., order/class, in such an example *Polychaeta*). Criteria used to score information were hence settled as follows:

- (i) for both taxonomical and spatio-temporal resolutions the discrete score can be 1 (i.e., missing data) or 0 (i.e., available data);
- (ii) for temporal coverage the continuous score was based on the presence of at least one record for each year included in the corresponding time range;
- (iii) for the spatial coverage the resulting continuous score was evaluated based on the absolute frequency of the number of [ICES statistical rectangles](#) having at least one observation by ICES ecoregion. ICES statistical

rectangles provide a grid covering the area between 36°N and 85°30'N and 44°W and 68°30'E, and therefore some Mediterranean Sea ecoregions are not fully covered. Indeed, an extension of the ICES statistical rectangles for all the highlighted ICES Ecoregions was firstly carried out to obtain a defined number of cells (i.e., ICES statistical rectangles) for each Ecoregion (Figure 7). The related shape files can be found in the COISPA GitHub repository ([link](#)).

Differently to discrete scores, continuous ones were calculated for both spatial and temporal coverages. Following the previous example, if we have multiple observations for each year from 2020 to 2024 (with equal spatial, temporal and taxonomic resolutions as described before), the final missing data score will be $1/6 = 0.16$ since we're missing only 2025. The same mechanism was applied to spatial coverage by counting the total number of cells within each ICES Ecoregion.

Figure 7 - Map showing the ICES Ecoregions with the ICES statistical rectangles.

The **selection process** acts as a filter to visualize different outcomes of the missing data assessment; this process allows the user to get enough flexibility to investigate the missing data percentages across different spatio-temporal coverages and resolutions. Notably, such a selection process should be the same for both drivers and response variable with the overarching goal of comparing results through the risk assessment step. However, in case of information with a default resolution, it is recommended to use this selection process filtering for the pertinent resolution; for instance, if the data to be assessed is an abundance index, which by its intrinsic nature does not consider resolutions at the level of geographical coordinates (intended as pure geometric point), it is advisable to filter for lower spatial resolution level

that, in this example, is “local, regional, by country or by sea”. This avoids counting a meaningless data as missing data, obtaining a balanced evaluation.

In the selection process it is possible to equally filter the two databases by levels of the classification factors, layers and/or species; which modifies the dimension of f directly affecting the $nrow$ and hence the denominator of the missing data’ fraction, which is actually the weight. This is the reason why no weighting methods based on the different number of levels were implemented in the score calculation.

3.2.4. Missing data Matrix

To facilitate the link between WP2 and WP4, a subset for each area of application was defined in accordance with DUCs’ design, which are then grouped within each **sub-area of application** in [Table 1](#). The conceptual design of the DUCs was provided in Deliverable 4.2 “Digital twin resources specification document”, describing the technical status of each DUC regarding its maturity and level of integration into the DTO infrastructure.

Table 1 - Main sub-areas of application and DUCs grouped in each area of application; first column is the header

area of application	Sustainable management of sea resources		Monitoring marine ecosystem health		Resilience of coastal communities to climate change and anthropogenic stressors			
sub-area of application	Mariculture sea resources	Natural sea resources (exploited by fishery and all the other human activities)	About all available marine species	About lower trophic level	Coastal communities management	Communities mainly affected by anthropogenic stressors	Communities strictly related to climate change	
DUCs	4.4_Spatial planning of sustainable mariculture 							

Scores were computed for the **missing data matrix** showing the results in percentage of missing data by ICES Ecoregion and taxa/driver analysed. Microsoft Excel® was used to visualize and eventually aggregate outcomes. The aggregation of these percentage results derives from the need to obtain a broader vision in both taxonomic and spatio-temporal terms; this technique allows us to directly apply different assessment approaches on the distribution of missing data, as the risk-based approach (see [section 3.3](#)). Such a technique is a useful shortcut to avoid re-running the analysis with a different selection process each time. In order to understand which statistical measures best describe the trend and distribution of the percentages of missing data (i.e., missing data matrix’s outcomes), preliminary analyses were conducted on each application presented in this deliverable, thus both on response variables and drivers. From these preliminaries analysis, the first quartile of the frequency distribution of the set of percentages appears to be very far from the second quartile (median) suggesting greater variability in the lower values of the distribution. It was hence decided to use the first quartile to show the results with different taxonomic, spatial and/or temporal aggregations, thus leading to a more feasible summary and valuable assessment application.

R scripts were developed to analyse each data source. The provided scripts should be considered as an example built for the purpose of this deliverable, however since such a methodology was developed to be flexible, a user could easily modify the code according to the needs and re-run the entire process. The main R script with relative outcomes is stored in the COISPA GitHub repository ([R script](#)) as an example on how to run the assessment. In the main script there is a specific section where the user can specify the type of response variable/driver and its features, as well as the classification factors. For each response variable/driver set, the following information will be automatically generated: 1) "records", a folder storing maps with the location of every single data downloaded, whether it is inside or outside the spatial domain; 2) "Outputs", a folder that includes the results of missing data matrices by time interval both in .csv and .xlsx formats; 3) "Rdata", where the R objects are saved. Finally, an [excel template](#) is provided containing all useful formulas, conditional formatting and plots for a better collection and visualization of the outcomes.

3.3. Impact assessment

The potential impact of missing data is assessed through a risk-based approach aimed at examining the applicability and suitability of digital solutions, considering different modelling approaches. Multiple risk assessment methods exist; their relevance, use, and definitions vary depending on the needs and purposes of the assessment and the information available to conduct the assessment. Objective-based risk assessment is commonly used to quantify and explore the effects of uncertainty (ICES, 2024) or of missing data in this specific context. The risk is calculated as a combination of: i) the missing data’s likelihood risk, which levels are defined based on the percentage of missing data resulting from the missing data matrix application for the selected coverage and resolution; ii) and the impact level on the modelling approach understood as severity in its general implementation. The resulting risk will contribute to examine the main consequences of missing data on general modelling approaches and their applicability within the DTO infrastructure.

3.3.1. Impacts definition (severity)

Three impacts’ levels were considered:

- **Minor_** impact is little with no or barely any effects;
- **Moderate_** effects are observable but not critical to model outcomes;
- **Major_** effect results in uncertain and/or critical effects on model outcomes.

The above levels of impact are inspired by general criteria based on literature (Araújo & Guisan, 2006; Peterson & Soberón, 2012) and expert judgment such as: the complexity of the tool, data needs, presence/absence of environmental/anthropogenic variables, expected outcomes. Following these criteria, and taking inspiration from the DUCs, different modelling approaches were allocated into six macro-groups to generalize the level of impact across areas of application: linear models, spatial distribution models, multispecies distribution models, ecological niche modelling, ecosystem modelling, and machine learning. Table 2 shows the impact associated to each macro-group. It should be noted that the macro-groups defined in table 2 have been designed for indicative purposes, aimed to broadly cluster potential analytical tools/products inspired from DUCs.

Table 2 - Impact table. First row (header) describes the impact levels, while first column refers to the Areas of Application.

Macro-group	Minor	Moderate	Major
Sustainable management of sea resources	linear models	multispecies distribution models	ecological niche modelling
			ecosystem modelling
Monitoring marine ecosystem health	spatial distribution models	multispecies distribution models	machine learning
Resilience of coastal communities to climate change and anthropogenic stressors	spatial distribution models	multispecies distribution models	ecological niche modelling
			machine learning

3.3.2. Likelihood definition

The likelihood to get missing data was calculated according to the missing data matrix results, designing three different levels based on the percentage of missing data at the first quartile:

- **Unlikely_** the percentage of missing data at the first quartile (25th percentile) is less than 33%;
- **Likely_** the percentage of missing data at the first quartile (25th percentile) is between 33% and 66%;

- **Very Likely**_ the percentage of missing data at the first quartile (25th percentile) is greater than 66%.

3.3.3. Risk rating key

Following the impact and likelihood definitions, a risk matrix was built by means of three different levels of risks (Figure 8):

- **Low**_ acceptable, it's possible to proceed;
- **Medium**_ it is possible to proceed but the uncertainty can be high;
- **High**_ robustness of the analysis is compromised, not possible to proceed.

The resulting risks act as warning indicators of the current feasibility of present and future products developed within the DTO-BioFlow framework. It should be noted that the average level of risk resulting from a 'very likely' likelihood is higher than the other levels; this choice is justified by the use of the first quartile as statistical metric for the aggregation of missing data matrix results (see [section 3.2.4](#)) which, looking at the distributions of missing data' percentages analysed in this deliverable, should tend towards a more precautionary level of risk.

		IMPACT		
		MINOR	MODERATE	MAJOR
		LITTLE TO NO EFFECT	EFFECTS ARE OBSERVABLE, BUT NOT CRITICAL TO OUTCOMES	EFFECTS RESULT IN UNCERTAIN/CRITICAL TO OUTCOMES
LIKELIHOOD	UNLIKELY	LOW	LOW	LOW
	MD <= 33%			
	LIKELY	LOW	LOW	MEDIUM
	33% < MD <= 66%			
VERY LIKELY	MEDIUM	MEDIUM	HIGH	
MD > 66%				

Figure 8 - Risk rating key. The columns represent the impact (i.e. severity), while rows indicate the likelihood of missing data (MD) for the selected variable (i.e. response variable/driver). Colours from light green to light red for the final risk assessment.

4. Examples of applications

4.1. Occurrence by phyla in EMODnet

The missing data matrix was applied to the interoperable data pool stored in EMODnet Biology. For this deliverable, the main response variable assessed was the occurrence of all the main phyla. The full classification for the occurrence of each taxon was downloaded from EMODnet biology directly into the R environment. Only the taxa with an accepted name, and hence with aphiaID (unique and persistent numerical identifier assigned to each scientific name within the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS; Vandepitte et al., 2015) and minimum temporal information (i.e., year of collection) were selected by query and downloaded. In the case where the total number of records for a taxon exceeded 1 million of occurrence records (maximum downloadable data capacity), the data have been downloaded as subsets by selecting the taxonomic levels immediately below and subsequently merged by phylum. A total of 96 phyla (of which 9

were downloaded as subsets) were analysed for a total of about 40 million records. Given the high variability in the total data analysis times, a progress bar has been implemented within the R code. For each batch of downloaded and analysed data, the progress bar estimates the remaining analysis time based on the durations of previous process. For each phylum, the resulting database was scored by selecting all the time ranges (i.e., temporal coverage) and all ICES Ecoregions (i.e., spatial coverage) at the highest spatio-temporal resolutions. Outcomes were analysed in the missing data matrices, and summarised in an excel file showing the percentage of missing data from 0% to 100% ([Missing data Matrix by TempCov ALL occurrence](#)). Furthermore, in a different excel sheet of the outcomes, a summary and radar plot of the first quartile values for each area and time range for all the taxa analysed are shown ("ALL PHYLA"). The last sheet "comparison" shows which are the cells with different values (in percentage) among the first 20 years of the 21st century (2000_2009, 2010_2019), when compared to the most recent time range (2020_2025).

In [Table 3](#) the summary of resulting missing data matrices for all the phyla included in EMODnet Biology by area and time range is shown. Looking at the spatial coverage distribution of missing data, seven Ecoregions appear to be poorly covered in term of biodiversity data: Aegean-Levantine Sea, Arctic Ocean, Azores, Faroes, Greenland Sea, Norwegian Sea, Ionian Sea and the Central Mediterranean Sea. About temporal coverage, it is observed that the distribution of missing data is concentrated in historical time intervals, particularly up to 1970, and in the last time range (i.e., 2020_2025). This result was expected given the difficulty of finding most current and historical data. It should be considered that the analysis performed on such an extremely vast level of taxonomic aggregation (i.e., 96 phyla) affects the final results; actually many taxa, mostly belonging to the kingdoms of Archea and Bacteria, were found to have a persistence of missing data throughout the entire time series increasing the overall percentage. It's interesting to note that, there is consistency in missing data percentages between the following time frames: 1970_1999, 2000_2009 and 2010_2019. This is not reflected into the last time range (2020_2025) for which the percentage increased towards 100% in all areas; the main reason for this could be linked to the time lag between data collection and data submission to EMODnet Biology. However, from the comparison table, a complete picture of which taxa are most affected by such a decreasing trend in data availability is provided; results highlighted that despite the higher number of taxa across space that show an increase in missing data compared to those in decline (on average there is a decrease of about 27%), more than 60% of these remain unchanged, whereas only about 5% show a high decrease level (missing data increase between 60% and 100%). This implies that the majority of missing data persists in space and time for specific taxa.

Table 3 - Summary of occurrence of missing data at phylum level by ICES Ecoregion (rows) and time range (columns). Percentage values are referring to the first quartile of the distribution of missing data for all phyla within selected time and space ranges. Cell's colours associate percentages with the likelihood risk definition ([section 3.3.2](#)). ICES Ecoregion are coloured by FAO Major Fishing Area, while time ranges are coloured by temporal aggregation ("Historical", "Present"; see [section 3.2.1.3](#))

ALL PHYLA	1880_1909	1910_1939	1940_1969	1970_1999	2000_2009	2010_2019	2020_2025
Adriatic Sea	100%	100%	100%	68%	51%	64%	73%
Aegean-Levantine Sea	100%	100%	100%	79%	86%	84%	100%
Arctic Ocean	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%
Azores	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	93%	100%
Baltic Sea	96%	100%	81%	29%	18%	16%	23%
Barents Sea	100%	100%	100%	59%	83%	70%	100%
Bay of Biscay and the Iberian Coast	100%	100%	100%	39%	37%	30%	50%
Black Sea	100%	100%	59%	53%	50%	56%	100%

Celtic Seas	100%	81%	58%	29%	23%	22%	56%
Faroes	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%
Greater North Sea	100%	100%	80%	24%	18%	17%	25%
Greenland Sea	100%	100%	100%	100%	69%	100%	100%
Iceland Sea	100%	100%	100%	56%	100%	100%	100%
Ionian Sea and the Central Mediterranean Sea	100%	100%	100%	86%	86%	85%	100%
Norwegian Sea	100%	100%	100%	93%	100%	83%	100%
Oceanic Northeast Atlantic	100%	100%	100%	41%	69%	100%	100%
Western Mediterranean Sea	100%	100%	58%	54%	36%	39%	100%

4.1.1. Occurrence by macro-groups

With the overarching goal to flow the missing data matrix' outcomes into the risk-based assessment, 7 taxonomic macro-groups were defined taking inspiration from DUC's designs: phytoplankton, zooplankton, benthic invertebrates, fish, crustaceans, macroalgae, cephalopods. Each taxonomic macro-group includes one or more phyla/classes/orders with a view to better represent these taxonomic aggregations. The resulting missing data matrices for each macro-group by area and time range with the information on the taxonomic aggregations adopted are provided ([Missing data Matrix by TempCov MACROGROUPs occurrence](#)) and discussed here.

When considering all ecoregions together from 1970 onwards, all macro-groups showed very low percentages of missing data. Going into the detail of each macro-region, the Arctic Ocean appears to be the only ecoregion with a high percentage of missing data. Exception is represented by the last time range (2020_2025) for which only 4 ecoregions (i.e., Baltic Sea, Barents Sea, Bay of Biscay and Iberian Coast, Celtic Sea) resulted in low percentages of missing data; but as discussed earlier, this may be due to the time lag between data collection and submission to EMODnet Biology. The situation changes considerably when looking before 1970, in fact the spatial coverage decreases both between taxonomic macro-groups and between macro-regions; the macro-groups accounting for the highest percentages of missing data are phytoplankton and cephalopods.

4.2. Metagenomics data by phyla & drivers in EMODnet

The same methodology was applied to all metagenomics data, and some drivers included in EMODnet platform. The drivers' selection was driven by the design of the modelling approaches used in the risk-based assessment. In this section each missing data matrix is briefly discussed to provide a more comprehensive view of the assessments presented in the following paragraph.

Metagenomics data, defined here as annotated occurrence data with DNA specification, were downloaded with EMODnet WFS and entered as input in the missing data matrix script. The analysis was performed on the same phyla and following the same selection process as described in [section 4.1](#). The outcomes indicate that for all ecoregions/macro-regions within different time ranges and for all macro-groups used, the percentage of missing data is extremely high. Such a result was pretty much expected since collection and integration of annotated DNA sequences into biodiversity databases, as well as the current maturity of DNA methodologies to derive biodiversity information have progressed substantially only in recent years (Abarenkov et al., 2023; Ruppert et al., 2019). Such a result is further consistent with some objectives of the DTO-BioFlow project that see prioritization of these DNA datasets in the ingestion process within the DTO' data lake (see Deliverable D2.9).

Since the majority of **drivers** included in the EMODnet catalogue are products in a raster format, and the main goal of EMODnet WFS is to offer a direct fine-grained access to geographic vector, it was not possible to use such a web service to download drivers info directly into R. To circumvent this issue the desired products were downloaded from the EMODnet catalogue; the following list of products/datasets for drivers of interest has been downloaded to finalize the risk-based assessments:

- Global ocean chlorophyll-a (https://ec.europa.eu/maritimeaffairs/atlas/maritime_atlas/#lang=EN;p=w;bkgd=1;theme=679:0.8;c=-1053920.54039797,5553491.350646372;z=4;e=t)
- Sea surface currents (<https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/geonetwork/srv/eng/catalog.search#/metadata/c48dcfc6-11cf-4f42-bf33-5af8e67995c6>)
- Seabed Habitat map (<https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/en/seabed-habitats>)
- Vessel density (<https://ows.emodnet-humanactivities.eu/geonetwork/srv/ita/catalog.search#/metadata/0f2f3ff1-30ef-49e1-96e7-8ca78d58a07c>)
- Fishing intensity (<https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/geonetwork/srv/ita/catalog.search#/metadata/d57fbdea-489e-4e11-9ff1-f0f706cfe783>)
- Bathymetry (<https://doi.org/10.12770/cf51df64-56f9-4a99-b1aa-36b8d7b743a1>)
- Global sea surface temperature (https://ec.europa.eu/maritimeaffairs/atlas/maritime_atlas/#lang=EN;p=w;bkgd=1;theme=920:0.75,999:0.05;c=314608.01401949674,6734902.059821764;z=3)

Each database was filtered in the selection process accounting for the coverage and resolution needed in the risk assessments (for details see [section 4.3](#)). Taxonomical resolution was removed from the selection criteria for drivers, while spatial resolution was fixed at the minimum level (“geom_shape”) to properly deal with raster data. All drivers scored an almost complete absence of missing data in the missing data matrix assessment. For sake of synthesis, only the exceptions will be discussed here. The main classification factor which scored partial values of missing data is the one of temporal coverage; indeed, some of the downloaded dataset referred to a specific time interval affecting the final score for these drivers. It’s the case of fishing intensity driver for which the temporal extension is from 2017 to 2023 (excluded), as well as vessel density starting in the same year but including also 2023 data. Also, for the habitat driver there is a difference in time coverage, but this is mainly due to the model itself that has been published in different versions over time in the EMODnet Seabed Habitats project; since 2009 six iterations of EUSeaMap (i.e., seabed habitat map) were developed (Vasquez et al., 2023) landing to the last one, here used, EUSeaMap 2023.

4.3. Risk-based assessment by area of application

As final step, a risk-based assessment of the impact of missing data was performed for each Area of Application (AofA), accounting for the likelihood level derived from the results of the missing data matrices ([section 4.1](#) & [4.2](#)). Risk assessment outcomes are detailed in the appendix ([section 7.3](#)). Getting inspired by DUCs designs, a general workflow for each AofA was built to better summarize the outcomes of the assessment and the links between different modelling approaches and response variable/drivers selected ([Figure 9](#), [Figure 10](#)

RESILIENCE OF COASTAL COMMUNITIES TO CLIMATE CHANGE AND ANTHROPOGENIC STRESSORS

Figure 11). These risk-based assessments were carried out on the present data pool (17-07-2025), results may thus change according to the time. In fact, the methodology presented here was designed to be a dynamic tool applicable over time.

The workflow of “Sustainable management of sea resources” (Figure 9) was designed to assess the feasibility of four different *modelling approaches*, each one more demanding in terms of data as their degree of complexity increases. In this example, the response variables considered were occurrence and biomass of three main taxonomic macro-groups related to the selected AofA: i.e., fish, macroalgae, benthic invertebrates. The less complex approach (i.e., linear modelling) requires data on the occurrence and biomass of fish as well as anthropogenic and environmental drivers (e.g., fishing pressure and seabed habitat). When increasing the level of complexity of the model (e.g., multispecies distribution models, complex ecosystem models), there is the need to include also information on occurrence and biomass of other target taxonomic groups or species. The assessment was conducted for the FAO major fishing area 27 (which includes the following ICES Ecoregions: Adriatic Sea, Aegean-Levantine Sea, Black Sea, Ionian Sea and Central Mediterranean Sea, Western Mediterranean Sea) for the period 2010-2025, considering the highest spatial and temporal resolutions, when applicable. The overall outcome indicates that while linear and multispecies distribution models scored a low level of risk, ecosystem and ecological niche models scored a medium level of overall risk which sees the highest likelihood from macroalgae occurrence data. Considering the different *modelling approach*, the final overall risk changes according to the complexity of the approach; indeed, the amount of data required to develop complex models (e.g., ecosystem model) is the main factor influencing the risk level. The same risk assessment was

carried out also for the remaining ICES ecoregions belonging to FAO major fishing area 37 in the same period and with identical resolutions. The risk-based outcomes did not diverge from the previous one.

SUSTAINABLE MANAGEMENT OF SEA RESOURCES

Figure 9 - Area of application: Sustainable management of sea resources. Modelling approaches potentially impacted by missing data, response variables related to different taxonomic groups, and drivers. On top-right the symbol legend. The different type of hatching corresponds to the different impact levels of modelling approaches.

Regarding the AofA “Monitoring marine ecosystem health” (Figure 10), as an example inspired by the DUCs, three modelling approaches covering three different impacts were highlighted. All need occurrence data on zooplankton and phytoplankton together with meaningful drivers as chlorophyll-a and sea surface currents; by increasing the complexity of the model, spatio-temporal abundance information should be provided for each of the selected taxa. The assessment was carried out in both FAO 27 and 37 areas in the period 2010_2025, considering the highest spatial and temporal resolutions, when applicable. In this case the outcomes describe a great situation where the scored risk is low for each element of the workflow, since the data availability and the suitability of the less complex modelling approaches (i.e., linear model, and multispecies distribution model) are adequate. However, once increasing the complexity of the modelling approach, the risk moved to medium level mainly due to the increased need for data.

MONITORING MARINE ECOSYSTEM HEALTH

Figure 10 - Area of application: Monitoring marine ecosystem health. Modelling approaches potentially impacted by missing data, response variables related to different taxonomic groups, and drivers. On top-right the symbol legend. The different type of hatching corresponds to the different impact levels of modelling approaches.

Referring to the last area of application “Resilience of coastal communities to climate change and anthropogenic stressors” (

RESILIENCE OF COASTAL COMMUNITIES TO CLIMATE CHANGE AND ANTHROPOGENIC STRESSORS

Figure 11), four different modelling approaches covering all impacts were considered. All required inputs of occurrence data originate both from direct observations and DNA sequences as well as drivers for bathymetry, sea surface temperature, and vessel density; in this AofA the main difference among the different modelling approaches is the amount of data demanded from each source. Indeed, this assessment was designed to target the broader taxonomical aggregation considering all the phyla at once in both FAO major fishing areas 27 and 37, and for the most recent period (2020_2025) at the highest resolutions, when applicable. Overall results indicated an average medium level of risk for all the modelling approaches excluding the more complex ones; once increasing the complexity of the model, the need of an important amount of data increases the risk to a high level. This is mainly caused by the huge presence of missing data especially for the DNA datasets; on the other side, as discussed in [section 4.2](#), the presence of missing data for this variable is mostly caused by the inclusion of DNA data in biodiversity databases, such as EMODnet, only recently having been proposed and facilitated by the DarwinCore standard. Furthermore, considering all phyla at once results in a significant increase of missing data which greatly impacts the applicability of complex modelling approaches.

RESILIENCE OF COASTAL COMMUNITIES TO CLIMATE CHANGE AND ANTHROPOGENIC STRESSORS

Figure 11 - Area of application: Resilience of coastal communities to climate change and anthropogenic stressors. Modelling approaches potentially impacted by missing data, response variables related to different taxonomic groups, and drivers. On top-right the symbol legend. The different type of hatching corresponds to the different impact levels of modelling approaches.

5. Conclusions

This deliverable outlines an assessment of the current missing data currently included in EMODnet in terms of coverage and resolution, with a specific focus on their impact in the feasibility of generalized digital solutions (i.e., modelling approaches) within the DTO-BioFlow infrastructure. The developed scripts and tools should be considered as an example, built for the purpose of this deliverable. Since the methodology was developed to be flexible, a hypothetical user could easily adapt the tools to its needs and re-run the entire process. This aspect is even more important when discussing outcomes, indeed the selection of broad taxonomic groups (e.g., phyla) was determined by the objective of this deliverable to assess the impact of missing data on a large scale; which obviously affected the results.

In respect to the percentage of missing data resulting from the application of missing data matrix on about 40 millions of occurrence data for 96 phyla currently included in EMODnet Biology, seven ecoregions were found to be poorly covered: Aegean-Levantine Sea, Arctic Ocean, Azores, Faroe, Greenland Sea, Norwegian Sea, Ionian Sea and the Central Mediterranean Sea. With regards to the 7 taxonomical macro-groups analysed (phytoplankton, zooplankton, benthic invertebrates, fish, crustaceans, macroalgae, cephalopods) the assessment on the status of missing data resulted in very low percentages from 1970 onwards except for the last time range (2020_2025).

The same assessment methodology was applied to metagenomics data and drivers included in EMODnet. In a nutshell, metagenomics data resulted in extremely high percentages of missing data probably due to the novelty of some biodiversity data collection and standardization methodologies. In contrast, most of the selected drivers resulted in very low percentages of missing data.

The results on the status of missing data were translated into likelihood based on gradual percentage limits; likelihoods were then combined with different impact levels associated with each digital solution proposed in each AofA to get the risk related to the applicability of a range of modelling approach. Overall, the level of risk was found to be between low and medium for all the areas of application, especially when considering specific taxonomical macro-groups and less complex modelling approaches such as linear models and multispecies distribution models. In contrast, the application of more complex approaches like machine learning, ecosystem modelling and ecological niche modelling may require mitigation measures, since the overall risk was high, especially when considering all the phyla. This underlines the importance of large and sustained flows of biodiversity data within EMODnet and hence into the EDITO infrastructure, to enable a well-functioning DTO. Through the integration of diverse response variables, drivers and modelling approaches in the missing data impact assessment, significant progress has been made towards ensuring an oceanic digital twin that can effectively support the EU to deliver on its biodiversity goals.

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7. Appendix

7.1. EMODnet layers

Appendix Table 1 – List available layers within EMODnet.

Thematic portal	Driver type	Layer	Comments
Bathymetry	Environmental	High Resolution Digital Terrain Model (HR-DTM)	The HR-DTM layer allows to zoom in deeper than the common DTM layer.
Bathymetry	Environmental	Underwater features	https://www.ngdc.noaa.gov/gazetteer/
Bathymetry	Environmental	Best-estimate European digital coastlines	containing best-estimate coastlines for the European seas at LAT (Lowest Astronomical Tide), MSL (Mean-Sea-Level), and MHW (Mean-High-Water).
Bathymetry	Anthropogenic	Wrecks	provided by OceanWise as proprietary WMS service and uses the UKHO Wrecks database as source
Geology	Environmental	Seabed substrate	5 classes: mud to muddy, sand, sand, coarse substrate, mixed sediment, rock and boulders
Geology	Environmental	Seabed accumulation rates	
Geology	Environmental	Seafloor lithology, stratigraphy and fault maps	Seafloor stratigraphy, lithology and fault maps representing the marine pre-Quaternary geological units, their age, structure and physical characteristics
Geology	Environmental	Coastal behavior	Satellite and Field data based Coastal behavior (Three coastal migration classes are defined – erosion, stable (<0.5 m of mean annual change), and accretion – which are accompanied by the level of accuracy (e.g. estimated, confirmed, no information) & Coastal types (four main classes: cliffs of rock or erosion-resistant consolidated sediment, sand and gravel beaches, muddy coasts, and coasts characterised by man-made structures)
Geology	Environmental	Geological events distributions	such as submarine landslides, fluid emissions, tectonics, earthquakes, tsunamis and volcanoes
Geology	Environmental	Mineral occurrences	marine aggregates, hydrocarbons, gas hydrates, placers, phosphorites, evaporites, polymetallic sulphides, polymetallic nodules, cobalt rich ferromanganese crust, metal rich sediment, sapropel, and vein hosted mineralisation.

Geology	Environmental	Submerged landscapes	26 classes of submerged landscape and palaeoenvironmental indicators ranging from mapped and modelled palaeocoastlines, evidence for submerged forests and peats, and submerged freshwater springs.
Geology	Environmental	Quaternary geology	Upper seafloor stratigraphy, lithology, and genesis maps representing the youngest marine Quaternary geological units, their age, genesis and physical characteristics.
Geology	Environmental	Geomorphology	two layers: (1) General physiographic features (e.g. continental shelf, continental slope, ridge) and (2) marine landforms (e.g. canyon, sea mount, delta lobe, moraine, esker) and their genesis.
Geology	Environmental	Boreholes locations	
Geology	Environmental	Seismic tracks	
Seabed Habitats	Environmental	Survey point data	
Seabed Habitats	Environmental	Broad-scale seabed habitat map	both EUNIS / full-detailed habitat classification and MSFD Benthic broad habitat types
Seabed Habitats	Environmental	Environmental variables influencing habitat type	optical properties (Light attenuation coefficient (KDPAR), Light (PAR) at the sea surface, Light (PAR) at the seabed), probability of the seabed being below the halocline (Baltic Sea only), kinetic energy at the seabed due to currents (Mediterranean, Macaronesia, Celtic Seas, North Sea, Channel, Biscay, Black Sea and Adriatic), kinetic energy at the seabed due to waves (Macaronesia, Celtic Seas, North Sea and Biscay), exposure index at the sea surface (Baltic Sea only), density of dissolved oxygen at the seabed (Baltic Sea only), from external providers (including kinetic energy due to waves and currents for various regions)
Seabed Habitats	Environmental	Collection of individual seabed habitat maps from surveys	Over 800 habitat maps collated from various sources, grouped according to habitat classification: EUNIS, Habitats Directive Annex I and Other.
Seabed Habitats	Environmental	Collection of modelled maps of specific habitats	Over 70 predictive habitat models of various habitats, collated from various sources, grouped according to sea region
Seabed Habitats	Environmental	Composite data products	priority habitats, including OSPAR threatened and/or declining habitats and Essential Ocean Variables (live coral, seagrass and macroalgae).
Physics	Environmental	Wave height and duration	

Physics	Environmental	Wind speed and direction	
Physics	Environmental	Sea temperature	SST
Physics	Environmental	Salinity	
Physics	Environmental	Sea Surface Currents	Horizontal speed of the water column
Physics	Environmental	Water clarity	Light Attenuation, turbidity, Total Suspended Matter (TSM)
Physics	Environmental	Changes in sea level	Relative and absolute sea level trends, plus anomalies
Physics	Environmental	River Runoff	Inflow from rivers
Physics	Environmental	Water conductivity / biochemical parameters	
Physics	Environmental	Atmospheric parameters	
Physics	Anthropogenic	Underwater noise	European Impulsive Noise Registry (licenced events such as pile driving, controlled explosions from naval)
Physics	Anthropogenic	Ice Extent and Ice-type	
Chemistry	Environmental	Acidity	Alkalinity and pH
Chemistry	Anthropogenic	Antifoulants	anthracene, tributyltin, etc..
Chemistry	Environmental	Chlorophyll	Eutrophication_Chlorophyll-a
Chemistry	Environmental	Dissolved gases	Eutrophication_dissolved inorganic nitrogen (DIN), dissolved oxygen
Chemistry	Anthropogenic	Fertilizers	hexachlorobenzene, etc..
Chemistry	Anthropogenic	Heavy metals	lead, mercury, cadmium

Chemistry	Anthropogenic	Hydrocarbons	anthracene, benzo[A]pyrene, fluoranthene, hexachlorobenzene, naphthalene
Chemistry	Anthropogenic	Marine litter (micro, beach, seafloor)	beach litter (litter list used - Mean total number of litter items - Composition of litter according to material categories in percent - Mean number of Cigarette - Mean number of Fishing - Mean number of Plastic bags), seafloor litter (Trawls locations Density - Material categories percentage per year - Fishing related items density - Plastic bags density)
Chemistry	Environmental	Organic matter	
Chemistry	Anthropogenic	Pesticides and biocides	DDT, etc..
Chemistry	Anthropogenic	Polychlorinated biphenyls	
Chemistry	Environmental	Radionuclides	14 Carbon
Human activities	Anthropogenic	Aggregate extraction	Gravel extracted per year, area of activity
Human activities	Anthropogenic	Algae production	macroalgae, microalgae, Spirulina
Human activities	Anthropogenic	Aquaculture	finfish, shellfish and freshwater production
Human activities	Anthropogenic	Cables	telecommunications cables (schematic routes, actual route locations), landing stations
Human activities	Anthropogenic	Cultural heritage	ship wrecks, lighthouses, submerged prehistoric archaeology and landscape
Human activities	Anthropogenic	Desalination plants	(Country, customer, feedwater, holding company, type, technology)
Human activities	Anthropogenic	Dredging	sites
Human activities	Anthropogenic	Energy	Nuclear Power Plants, Ocean energy project Locations, Ocean energy test sites, Wind Farms
Human activities	Anthropogenic	Environment	Protected areas, state of bathing water

Human activities	Anthropogenic	Fisheries	Fisheries zones (ICES and FAO nomenclature), Fish Catches, fish sales, fishing effort, fishing intensity
Human activities	Anthropogenic	Hydrocarbon extraction	Oil and Gas: active licences, boreholes, offshore installations
Human activities	Anthropogenic	Main ports	Traffic
Human activities	Anthropogenic	Maritime Spatial Planning (MSP)	Spatial Plan Areas, Zoning Areas, lines and locations
Human activities	Anthropogenic	Military Areas	
Human activities	Anthropogenic	Ocean energy facilities	project locations and test sites
Human activities	Anthropogenic	Other forms of area management/designation	advisory councils, international conventions, maritime boundaries, MSFD reporting units, Exclusive Economic Zones
Human activities	Anthropogenic	Pipelines	
Human activities	Anthropogenic	Waste disposal	dredge spoil dumping, dumped munitions, waste at ports, urban wastewater discharge points and treatment plants
Human activities	Anthropogenic	Shipping Density	Vessels and Routes Density
Human activities	Anthropogenic	Wind farms	

7.2. DTO's georeferenced marine regions: an investigation on suitable biogeographic domains

Following the monthly meeting of the WP2 held online last February 9 (2024), the group expressed the need to determine a standard for georeferenced marine regions within the DTO-BioFlow framework. The development of a unique georeferenced standard of marine place names and areas have become indispensable in managing and displaying marine data and information (Claus et al., 2014). Indeed, the absence of a default georeferenced standard hampering several marine geographic applications, for example the linking of locations to databases to integrate data (Chapman & Wieczorek, 2020). Such a challenge is in line with the planned workflow of the project aiming to develop a sustainable integration of existing and new Artificial Intelligence processed and automated data flows from various sources to EMODnet and into the EDITO infrastructure serving the EU DTO. The group agreed to determine a spatial domain that is in accordance not only with EMODnet default geographical standards, but also with the biogeographical aspects for the collection, organization, analysis and modelling of biodiversity data and associated pressures.

This document aims to show an initial overview of some suitable marine spatial domain for DTO works/tasks, summarizing the main features and providing a little focus on the best option available so far.

As was pointed out during the meeting, the desired spatial units should be flexible enough to consider both geographical macro scales and regional/local ones; furthermore, they should agree with EMODnet's standard layers about ecosystem and anthropogenic dynamics.

Appendix Table 2 shows the main features of some of the most common spatial domains currently adopted in European marine data management and research.

The results of this brief investigation show that the ecoregions defined by ICES can be the suitable option available. In fact, following their definition and rationale, these space units were designed not only to provide the evidence for an ecosystem-based approach in accordance with the spatial management definitions and supra-national Legislation (e.g. the EU Marine Strategy Framework Directive, MSFD), but also to solve regional scientific challenges. Therefore, from 2004 when the first ICES' ecoregions were designed (ICES, 2004), these spatial units were adapted slowly and occasionally in response to changes in management areas and through dialogues with regional managers, reaching the current shaping in 2015 (ICES, 2020).

Currently, the individual characteristics of ICES ecoregions are used to provide science advice to environmental ministries and international agencies, (e.g. EU DG ENV, OSPAR, etc.) and to fisheries ministries, agencies, and regional fisheries organizations. Therefore, it is possible to identify within them, sub-areas in agreement not only with the MSFD, but also with FAO sub-areas, divisions, and subdivisions (Figure 5). Finally, these ecoregions are currently available as layers within the EMODnet platform, thus facilitating data ingestion and promoting the flow of data within the DTO-BioFlow' pipeline.

Appendix Table 2. Main informative layers, geographical scales and dynamics of some of the most adopted marine spatial domains in EU project and in the management of marine areas.

Framework/ Organization	Mapping	Main informative layers	Geographical scale (macro)	Geographical scale (regional/local)	ecosystem dynamics	fishery dynamics	others anthropogenic dynamics	link
EMODnet Biology	marine regions	EEZ, territorial seas (12NM), Contiguous Zones (24NM), Internal waters, Extended Continental Shelves (ECS), International Hydrographic Organization	Y	Y	Y	N	Y	🔗
EMODnet Seabed Habitats	EU sea map	Marine regions and subregions from MSFD, EUNIS habitat classification	Y	N	Y	N	N	🔗
EMODnet Human Activities	EU Human activities	Marine regions and subregions from MSFD, divisions and subdivisions of FAO Major Fishing areas	Y	N	N	Y	Y	🔗
ICES	ICES statistical ecoregions	ICES statistical rectangles, EEZ, divisions and subdivisions of FAO Major Fishing areas, Large Marine Ecosystems (LMEs) areas, marine regions and subregions from MSFD	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	🔗 🔗 🔗
Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD)	GES areas	National waters, North-East Atlantic maritime areas defined by OSPAR convention	Y	partial (regional but not local)	N	N	N	🔗
FAO	FAO Major Fishing Statistical Areas	FAO sub-areas, divisions, and subdivisions	Y	Y	N	Y	N	🔗
European Environment Agency (EEA)	Regional seas around Europe V2, (Oct 2022)	marine regions and subregions from MSFD, ICES Ecoregions, Regional Sea Conventions	Y	partial (regional but not local)	Y	Y	Y	🔗

7.2.1. References

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ICES. 2004. Information and advice about appropriate eco-regions for the implementation of an ecosystem approach in European waters. In Report of the ICES Advisory Committee on Fishery Management and Advisory Committee on Ecosystems, 2004. ICES Advice, section 2.1.2.1. Volume 1, Number 2: 115–131.

ICES. 2020. Definition and rationale for ICES ecoregions. In Report of the ICES Advisory Committee, 2020. ICES Advice 2020, Section 1.4. <https://doi.org/10.17895/ices.advice.6014>

7.3. Risk Assessment

AREA OF APPLICATION

DUCs involved

Sustainable management of sea resources

4.4_Spatial planning of sustainable mariculture,
4.5_Ecosystem-based spatial planning and MPA management

					RISK ASSESSMENT		
PRODUCT	RESPONSE VAR	DRIVER	SPATIO-TEMPORAL COVERAGE	SPATIO-TEMPORAL RESOLUTION	IMPACT	LIKELIHOOD	RISK LEVEL
Linear model	occurence_FISH		FAO 37 2010_2019, 2020_2025	daily/weekly geo coordinates	MINOR	LIKELY	LOW

Linear model	spatio-temporal biomass_FISH		FAO 37 2010_2019, 2020_2025	annual/multi-annual geo shapes	MINOR	LIKELY	LOW
Linear model		SEABED HABITAT	FAO 37 2010_2019, 2020_2025	annual/multi-annual geo shapes	MINOR	LIKELY	LOW
Multispecies distribution model	occurrence_FISH		FAO 37 2010_2019, 2020_2025	daily/weekly geo coordinates	MODERATE	LIKELY	LOW
Multispecies distribution model	spatio-temporal biomass_FISH		FAO 37 2010_2019, 2020_2025	annual/multi-annual geo shapes	MODERATE	LIKELY	LOW
Multispecies distribution model	spatio-temporal biomass_CRUSTACEAN		FAO 37 2010_2019, 2020_2025	annual/multi-annual geo shapes	MODERATE	LIKELY	LOW
Multispecies distribution model		FISHING PRESSURE	FAO 37 2010_2019, 2020_2025	annual/multi-annual geo shapes	MODERATE	LIKELY	LOW
Multispecies distribution model		SEABED HABITAT	FAO 37 2010_2019, 2020_2025	annual/multi-annual geo shapes	MODERATE	LIKELY	LOW
ecosystem modeling ecological niche modeling	occurrence_FISH		FAO 37 2010_2019, 2020_2025	daily/weekly geo coordinates	MAJOR	LIKELY	MEDIUM
ecosystem modeling ecological niche modeling	occurrence_MACROALGAE		FAO 37 2010_2019, 2020_2025	daily/weekly geo coordinates	MAJOR	LIKELY	MEDIUM

ecosystem modeling ecological niche modeling	occurrence_BENTHIC INVERTEBRATES		FAO 37 2010_2019, 2020_2025	daily/weekly geo coordinates	MAJOR	LIKELY	MEDIUM
ecosystem modeling ecological niche modeling	spatio-temporal biomass_FISH		FAO 37 2010_2019, 2020_2025	annual/multi-annual geo shapes	MAJOR	LIKELY	MEDIUM
ecosystem modeling ecological niche modeling	spatio-temporal biomass_CRUSTACEAN		FAO 37 2010_2019, 2020_2025	annual/multi-annual geo shapes	MAJOR	LIKELY	MEDIUM
ecosystem modeling ecological niche modeling		FISHING PRESSURE	FAO 37 2010_2019, 2020_2025	annual/multi-annual geo shapes	MAJOR	LIKELY	MEDIUM
ecosystem modeling ecological niche modeling		SEABED HABITAT	FAO 37 2010_2019, 2020_2025	annual/multi-annual geo shapes	MAJOR	LIKELY	MEDIUM

					RISK ASSESSMENT		
PRODUCT	RESPONSE VAR	DRIVER	SPATIO-TEMPORAL COVERAGE	SPATIO-TEMPORAL RESOLUTION	IMPACT	LIKELIHOOD	RISK LEVEL
Linear model	occurrence_FISH		FAO 27 2010_2019, 2020_2025	daily/weekly geo coordinates	MINOR	UNLIKELY	LOW

Linear model	spatio-temporal biomass_FISH		FAO 27 2010_2019, 2020_2025	annual/multi-annual geo shapes	MINOR	LIKELY	LOW
Linear model		SEABED HABITAT	FAO 27 2010_2019, 2020_2025	annual/multi-annual geo shapes	MINOR	LIKELY	LOW
Multispecies distribution model	occurrence_FISH		FAO 27 2010_2019, 2020_2025	daily/weekly geo coordinates	MODERATE	UNLIKELY	LOW
Multispecies distribution model	spatio-temporal biomass_FISH		FAO 27 2010_2019, 2020_2025	annual/multi-annual geo shapes	MODERATE	LIKELY	LOW
Multispecies distribution model	spatio-temporal biomass_CRUSTACEAN		FAO 27 2010_2019, 2020_2025	annual/multi-annual geo shapes	MODERATE	LIKELY	LOW
Multispecies distribution model		FISHING PRESSURE	FAO 27 2010_2019, 2020_2025	annual/multi-annual geo shapes	MODERATE	LIKELY	LOW
Multispecies distribution model		SEABED HABITAT	FAO 27 2010_2019, 2020_2025	annual/multi-annual geo shapes	MODERATE	LIKELY	LOW
ecosystem modeling ecological niche modeling	occurrence_FISH		FAO 27 2010_2019, 2020_2025	daily/weekly geo coordinates	MAJOR	UNLIKELY	LOW
ecosystem modeling ecological niche modeling	occurrence_MACROALGAE		FAO 27 2010_2019, 2020_2025	daily/weekly geo coordinates	MAJOR	LIKELY	MEDIUM

ecosystem modeling ecological niche modeling	occurrence_BENTHIC INVERTEBRATES		FAO 27 2010_2019, 2020_2025	daily/weekly geo coordinates	MAJOR	LIKELY	MEDIUM
ecosystem modeling ecological niche modeling	spatio-temporal biomass_FISH		FAO 27 2010_2019, 2020_2025	annual/multi-annual geo shapes	MAJOR	LIKELY	MEDIUM
ecosystem modeling ecological niche modeling	spatio-temporal biomass_CRUSTACEAN		FAO 27 2010_2019, 2020_2025	annual/multi-annual geo shapes	MAJOR	LIKELY	MEDIUM
ecosystem modeling ecological niche modeling		FISHING PRESSURE	FAO 27 2010_2019, 2020_2025	annual/multi-annual geo shapes	MAJOR	LIKELY	MEDIUM
ecosystem modeling ecological niche modeling		SEABED HABITAT	FAO 27 2010_2019, 2020_2025	annual/multi-annual geo shapes	MAJOR	LIKELY	MEDIUM

AREA OF APPLICATION

DUCs involved

Monitoring marine ecosystem health	4.3_Assessing pelagic biodiversity and human impact, 4.6_Lower-trophic level biomass monitoring to inform ocean governance
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RISK ASSESSMENT

PRODUCT	RESPONSE VAR	DRIVER	SPATIO-TEMPORAL COVERAGE	SPATIO-TEMPORAL RESOLUTION	IMPACT	LIKELIHOOD	RISK LEVEL
Spatial distribution model	occurrence_PHYTOPLANKTON		FAO 37 2010_2019, 2020_2025	daily/weekly geo coordinates	MINOR	LIKELY	LOW
Spatial distribution model	occurrence_ZOOPLANKTON		FAO 37 2010_2019, 2020_2025	daily/weekly geo coordinates	MINOR	LIKELY	LOW
Spatial distribution model		CHLOROPHYLL- α	FAO 37 2010_2019, 2020_2025	daily/weekly geo shapes	MINOR	UNLIKELY	LOW
Spatial distribution model		SEA SURFACE CURRENTS	FAO 37 2010_2019, 2020_2025	daily/weekly geo shapes	MINOR	UNLIKELY	LOW
Multispecies distribution model	occurrence_PHYTOPLANKTON		FAO 37 2010_2019, 2020_2025	daily/weekly geo coordinates	MODERATE	LIKELY	LOW
Multispecies distribution model	occurrence_ZOOPLANKTON		FAO 37 2010_2019, 2020_2025	daily/weekly geo coordinates	MODERATE	LIKELY	LOW
Multispecies distribution model	spatio-temporal abundance_ZOOPLANKTON		FAO 37 2010_2019, 2020_2025	annual/multi- annual geo shapes	MODERATE	LIKELY	LOW
Multispecies distribution model	spatio-temporal abundance_PHYTOPLANKTON		FAO 37 2010_2019, 2020_2025	annual/multi- annual geo shapes	MODERATE	LIKELY	LOW

Multispecies distribution model		CHLOROPHYLL-a	FAO 37 2010_2019, 2020_2025	daily/weekly geo shapes	MODERATE	UNLIKELY	LOW
Multispecies distribution model		SEA SURFACE CURRENTS	FAO 37 2010_2019, 2020_2025	daily/weekly geo shapes	MODERATE	UNLIKELY	LOW
Machine Learning	occurence_PHYTOPLANKTON		FAO 37 2010_2019, 2020_2025	daily/weekly geo coordinates	MAJOR	LIKELY	MEDIUM
Machine Learning	occurence_ZOOPLANKTON		FAO 37 2010_2019, 2020_2025	daily/weekly geo coordinates	MAJOR	LIKELY	MEDIUM
Machine Learning	spatio-temporal abundance_ZOOPLANKTON		FAO 37 2010_2019, 2020_2025	annual/multi- annual geo shapes	MAJOR	LIKELY	MEDIUM
Machine Learning	spatio-temporal abundance_PHYTOPLANKTON		FAO 37 2010_2019, 2020_2025	annual/multi- annual geo shapes	MAJOR	LIKELY	MEDIUM
Machine Learning		CHLOROPHYLL-a	FAO 37 2010_2019, 2020_2025	daily/weekly geo shapes	MAJOR	UNLIKELY	LOW
Machine Learning		SEA SURFACE CURRENTS	FAO 37 2010_2019, 2020_2025	daily/weekly geo shapes	MAJOR	UNLIKELY	LOW

					RISK ASSESSMENT		
PRODUCT	RESPONSE VAR	DRIVER	SPATIO-TEMPORAL COVERAGE	SPATIO-TEMPORAL RESOLUTION	IMPACT	LIKELIHOOD	RISK LEVEL
Spatial distribution model	occurence_PHYTOPLANKTON		FAO 27 2010_2019, 2020_2025	daily/weekly geo coordinates	MINOR	LIKELY	LOW
Spatial distribution model	occurence_ZOOPLANKTON		FAO 27 2010_2019, 2020_2025	daily/weekly geo coordinates	MINOR	LIKELY	LOW
Spatial distribution model		CHLOROPHYLL-a	FAO 27 2010_2019, 2020_2025	daily/weekly geo shapes	MINOR	UNLIKELY	LOW
Spatial distribution model		SEA SURFACE CURRENTS	FAO 27 2010_2019, 2020_2025	daily/weekly geo shapes	MINOR	UNLIKELY	LOW
Multispecies distribution model	occurence_PHYTOPLANKTON		FAO 27 2010_2019, 2020_2025	daily/weekly geo coordinates	MODERATE	LIKELY	LOW
Multispecies distribution model	occurence_ZOOPLANKTON		FAO 27 2010_2019, 2020_2025	daily/weekly geo coordinates	MODERATE	LIKELY	LOW
Multispecies distribution model	spatio-temporal abundance_ZOOPLANKTON		FAO 27 2010_2019, 2020_2025	annual/multi- annual geo shapes	MODERATE	LIKELY	LOW

Multispecies distribution model	spatio-temporal abundance_PHYTOPLANKTON		FAO 27 2010_2019, 2020_2025	annual/multi-annual geo shapes	MODERATE	LIKELY	LOW
Multispecies distribution model		CHLOROPHYLL- α	FAO 27 2010_2019, 2020_2025	daily/weekly geo shapes	MODERATE	UNLIKELY	LOW
Multispecies distribution model		SEA SURFACE CURRENTS	FAO 27 2010_2019, 2020_2025	daily/weekly geo shapes	MODERATE	UNLIKELY	LOW
Machine Learning	occurrence_PHYTOPLANKTON		FAO 27 2010_2019, 2020_2025	daily/weekly geo coordinates	MAJOR	LIKELY	MEDIUM
Machine Learning	occurrence_ZOOPLANKTON		FAO 27 2010_2019, 2020_2025	daily/weekly geo coordinates	MAJOR	LIKELY	MEDIUM
Machine Learning	spatio-temporal abundance_ZOOPLANKTON		FAO 27 2010_2019, 2020_2025	annual/multi-annual geo shapes	MAJOR	LIKELY	MEDIUM
Machine Learning	spatio-temporal abundance_PHYTOPLANKTON		FAO 27 2010_2019, 2020_2025	annual/multi-annual geo shapes	MAJOR	LIKELY	MEDIUM
Machine Learning		CHLOROPHYLL- α	FAO 27 2010_2019, 2020_2025	daily/weekly geo shapes	MAJOR	UNLIKELY	LOW
Machine Learning		SEA SURFACE CURRENTS	FAO 27 2010_2019, 2020_2025	daily/weekly geo shapes	MAJOR	UNLIKELY	LOW

AREA OF APPLICATION

DUCs involved

Resilience of coastal communities to climate change and anthropogenic stressors

4.1_Invasive species management,
4.2_Impact from offshore infrastructures,
4.7_Ecosystem services, including carbon sequestration

					RISK ASSESSMENT		
PRODUCT	RESPONSE VAR	DRIVER	SPATIO-TEMPORAL COVERAGE	SPATIO-TEMPORAL RESOLUTION	IMPACT	LIKELIHOOD	RISK LEVEL
spatial distribution model	occurrence_ALL PHYLA		FAO 37 2020_2025	daily/weekly geo coordinates	MINOR	VERY LIKELY	MEDIUM
spatial distribution model	DNA_ALL PHYLA		FAO 27 2020_2025	daily/weekly geo coordinates	MINOR	VERY LIKELY	MEDIUM
spatial distribution model		BATHYMETRY	FAO 37 2020_2026	annual/multi-annual geo shapes	MINOR	UNLIKELY	LOW
spatial distribution model		SEA SURFACE TEMPERATURE	FAO 27 2020_2026	daily/weekly geo shapes	MINOR	UNLIKELY	LOW
spatial distribution model		VESSEL DENSITY	FAO 37 2020_2027	daily/weekly geo shapes	MINOR	LIKELY	LOW

multispecies distribution model	occurence_ALL PHYLA		FAO 27 2020_2027	daily/weekly geo coordinates	MODERATE	VERY LIKELY	MEDIUM
multispecies distribution model	DNA_ALL PHYLA		FAO 37 2020_2028	daily/weekly geo coordinates	MODERATE	VERY LIKELY	MEDIUM
multispecies distribution model		BATHYMETRY	FAO 27 2020_2028	annual/multi-annual geo shapes	MODERATE	UNLIKELY	LOW
multispecies distribution model		SEA SURFACE TEMPERATURE	FAO 37 2020_2029	daily/weekly geo shapes	MODERATE	UNLIKELY	LOW
multispecies distribution model		VESSEL DENSITY	FAO 27 2020_2029	daily/weekly geo shapes	MODERATE	LIKELY	LOW
ecological niche modeling machine Learning	occurence_ALL PHYLA		FAO 37 2020_2030	daily/weekly geo coordinates	MAJOR	VERY LIKELY	HIGH
ecological niche modeling machine Learning	DNA_ALL PHYLA		FAO 27 2020_2030	daily/weekly geo coordinates	MAJOR	VERY LIKELY	HIGH
ecological niche modeling machine Learning		BATHYMETRY	FAO 37 2020_2031	annual/multi-annual geo shapes	MAJOR	UNLIKELY	LOW
ecological niche modeling machine Learning		SEA SURFACE TEMPERATURE	FAO 27 2020_2031	daily/weekly geo shapes	MAJOR	UNLIKELY	LOW

ecological niche modeling machine Learning		VESSEL DENSITY	FAO 37 2020_2032	daily/weekly geo shapes	MAJOR	LIKELY	MEDIUM
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					RISK ASSESSMENT		
PRODUCT	RESPONSE VAR	DRIVER	SPATIO-TEMPORAL COVERAGE	SPATIO-TEMPORAL RESOLUTION	IMPACT	LIKELIHOOD	RISK LEVEL
spatial distribution model	occurence_ALL PHYLA		FAO 27 2020_2025	daily/weekly geo coordinates	MINOR	VERY LIKELY	MEDIUM
spatial distribution model	DNA_ALL PHYLA		FAO 27 2020_2025	daily/weekly geo coordinates	MINOR	VERY LIKELY	MEDIUM
spatial distribution model		BATHYMETRY	FAO 27 2020_2025	annual/multi-annual geo shapes	MINOR	UNLIKELY	LOW
spatial distribution model		SEA SURFACE TEMPERATURE	FAO 27 2020_2025	daily/weekly geo shapes	MINOR	UNLIKELY	LOW
spatial distribution model		VESSEL DENSITY	FAO 27 2020_2025	daily/weekly geo shapes	MINOR	LIKELY	LOW
multispecies distribution model	occurence_ALL PHYLA		FAO 27 2020_2025	daily/weekly geo coordinates	MODERATE	VERY LIKELY	MEDIUM

multispecies distribution model	DNA_ALL PHYLA		FAO 27 2020_2025	daily/weekly geo coordinates	MODERATE	VERY LIKELY	MEDIUM
multispecies distribution model		BATHYMETRY	FAO 27 2020_2025	annual/multi-annual geo shapes	MODERATE	UNLIKELY	LOW
multispecies distribution model		SEA SURFACE TEMPERATURE	FAO 27 2020_2025	daily/weekly geo shapes	MODERATE	UNLIKELY	LOW
multispecies distribution model		VESSEL DENSITY	FAO 27 2020_2025	daily/weekly geo shapes	MODERATE	LIKELY	LOW
ecological niche modeling machine Learning	occurence_ALL PHYLA		FAO 27 2020_2025	daily/weekly geo coordinates	MAJOR	VERY LIKELY	HIGH
ecological niche modeling machine Learning	DNA_ALL PHYLA		FAO 27 2020_2025	daily/weekly geo coordinates	MAJOR	VERY LIKELY	HIGH
ecological niche modeling machine Learning		BATHYMETRY	FAO 27 2020_2025	annual/multi-annual geo shapes	MAJOR	UNLIKELY	LOW
ecological niche modeling machine Learning		SEA SURFACE TEMPERATURE	FAO 27 2020_2025	daily/weekly geo shapes	MAJOR	UNLIKELY	LOW
ecological niche modeling machine Learning		VESSEL DENSITY	FAO 27 2020_2025	daily/weekly geo shapes	MAJOR	LIKELY	MEDIUM

DTO-BioFlow

Integration of biodiversity monitoring data into the Digital Twin Ocean

